

PHYSICOCHEMICAL ANALYSIS OF CHARRU MUSSEL (*Mytella strigata*) POWDER AND ITS ACCEPTABILITY AS KROPEK

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ABSTRACT

The study aimed to utilize the abundant and invasive *Mytella strigata* found in the Panguil Bay area by incorporating their powder into a processed product, kropek. The physicochemical properties of the *Mytella strigata* powder were analyzed, revealing a pH of 6.32, a bulk density of 0.456 g/cm³, and a moisture content of 5.11%. An experimental research design with 30 respondents was employed to evaluate the sensory qualities of three formulations: (1) 20% *Mytella strigata* powder and 80% cassava flour, (2) 30% *Mytella strigata* powder and 70% cassava flour, and (3) 40% *Mytella strigata* and 60% Cassava powder. The results showed that Formulation 1 was significantly preferred in terms of appearance ($F=4.79$, $p<0.05$) and crispiness ($F=3.82$, $p<0.05$). While there were no significant differences in aroma, color, or taste, the overall acceptability was higher for Formulation 1. The study suggests that lowering the amount of *Mytella strigata* powder in the product could further improve its sensory qualities and that determining the shelf-life of the *Mytella strigata* powder would be necessary for commercial viability. The research study provides a potential solution to address the underutilization of the invasive *Mytella strigata* by incorporating their powder into a popular local snack, kropek. The findings highlight the feasibility of using *Mytella strigata* powder in food product development, with further optimization and commercialization opportunities.

Keywords: *Acceptability level, Kropek, Mytella strigata powder, Physicochemical analysis*

INTRODUCTION

The fishing community in Tangub City has faced significant challenges due to the proliferation of *Mytella strigata*, a species of mussel that has become a growing problem in the region. These mussels clog fish nets, reducing the oxygen available to farmed species such as oysters and milkfish, and hampering the efficiency of aquaculture operations. The dense accumulation of *Mytella strigata* also leads to additional costs for farmers, who must hire assistants to remove the mussels from their nets, highlighting the labor-intensive nature of dealing with this invasive species.

Despite its historical significance, *Mytella strigata* is traditionally consumed in local dishes such as "kinilaw" and "adobo." However, its relatively small size and suboptimal meat quality have limited its culinary appeal when compared to other mussel species. To address this limitation, the researcher explored the innovative application of *Mytella strigata* powder in the production of kropek, a popular snack food in Southeast and East Asia.

Kropek, traditionally a dried product made from ground rice, shrimp, or fish, has evolved into a snack food crafted from ground, flavored tapioca that was shaped and fried (Espejo & Hermes, 1998). This snack food holds cultural significance and is widely enjoyed by people of all ages (Estrella, 2022). In the Philippines, there has been a 13% increase in snacking between 2015 and 2017, indicating a growing demand for acceptable kropek with superior sensory attributes (Taewee, 2011; Adobo Magazine, 2017).

From a practical standpoint, consumers often seek ready-to-eat snacks, quick meals, and easy-to-cook items to optimize their limited cooking time, particularly in the workplace. However, consumers tend to overlook the nutritional content of these processed snacks, which can vary significantly depending on the methods of preparation and processing (Ogunola et al., 2012).

On the other hand, the physicochemical properties of food powders, such as pH, bulk density, and moisture content, play crucial roles in determining their functionality and application in food processing. Foods in powder form are convenient to transport and store, and their extended shelf life reduces wastage and promotes sustainable development (Ueda et al., 2023). The physicochemical properties of food powders, encompassing particle size, shape, and surface characteristics, significantly influence their functional and sensory properties and behavior during processing and storage (Roos & Drusch, 2015). Moisture content is a crucial factor influencing the stability and shelf-life of food powders, as excessive moisture can lead to microbial growth and spoilage (Barbosa-Cánovas et al., 2005).

By incorporating *Mytella strigata* powder into the production of kropek, this study aims to enhance the utility and acceptance of this underutilized species in processed food products, thereby making a substantial impact on the food industry and inspiring new possibilities for *Mytella strigata* utilization.

Research Questions

This study sought to determine the acceptability of the proposed innovative product from *Mytella strigata* powder.

1. What are the physicochemical properties of the powdered *Mytella strigata* in terms of:
 - a. bulk density;
 - b. pH;
 - c. color evaluation; and
 - d. moisture content?
2. What is the level of acceptability of the *Mytella strigata* kropek in terms of sensory evaluation (appearance, aroma, color, taste, and crispiness) and in terms of the following formulation:
 - a. 20% *Mytella strigata* Powder; 80 % Cassava Flour;
 - b. 30% *Mytella strigata* Powder; 70% Cassava Flour; and
 - c. 40% *Mytella strigata* Powder; 60% Cassava Flour?
3. Is there a significant difference among treatments regarding appearance, aroma, color, taste, and crispiness?

METHODOLOGY

The study employed descriptive statistics, such as mean and standard deviation, to evaluate the acceptability of products incorporated with *Mytella strigata* powder across various formulations. Additionally, inferential statistics, specifically Analysis of Variance (ANOVA), were used to analyze differences in acceptability among the different formulations of the *Mytella strigata* powder as kropek.

The physicochemical analysis of the *Mytella strigata* powder was conducted in an accredited laboratory. The study utilized purposive sampling with thirty (30) semi-trained food individuals from the University of Science and Technology of Southern Philippines. This group consisted of fifteen (15) students and fifteen (15) teachers, all involved in food-related courses or research.

Before the commencement of the sensory evaluation, the researcher thoroughly and transparently explained the study's objectives and procedures. Participants were explicitly informed that their participation was entirely voluntary and that they could withdraw from the study without facing any adverse consequences. Random codes were systematically assigned to each treatment according to a master list to ensure impartiality and eliminate bias during the sensory evaluation. The respondents evaluated the samples' degree of liking using the 9-point hedonic scale, as developed by Peryam and Pilgrim (1957) as a well-established tool rigorously validated for sensory evaluation and acceptability assessment.

The respondents evaluated the acceptability of Kropek with varying formulations: 20% *Mytella strigata* powder and 80% cassava flour; 30% *Mytella strigata* powder and 70% cassava flour and 40% *Mytella strigata* powder and 60% cassava flour—based on five (5) key food attributes: appearance, aroma, color, taste, and crispiness. These attributes served as the parameters for determining overall preference for the formulated Kropek formulations.

Range of Score	Verbal Interpretation
8.12 - 9.00	Like Extremely
7.23 - 8.11	Like Very much
6.34 - 7.22	Like Moderately
5.45 - 6.33	Like slightly
4.56 - 5.44	Neither like nor Dislike
3.67 - 4.55	Dislike slightly
2.78 - 3.66	Dislike much
1.89 - 2.77	Dislike Very Much
1.00 - 1.88	Dislike Extremely

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Research Question 1. What are the physicochemical properties of the powdered *Mytella strigata* in terms of:

- a. bulk density;
- b. pH;
- c. color evaluation; and
- d. moisture content?

Table 1

Physicochemical properties of Mytella strigata Powder in terms of pH, Bulk density, and Moisture content

Parameters	Unit	Results	Test Method
ph	-	6.32 @25.6°C	Electrometry
Bulk Density	g/cm ³	0.456	Modified Core Method
Moisture Content	%	5.11	Air Oven Drying

Table 1 shows the result that *Mytella strigata* powder has a recorded pH value of 6.32 @ 25.6 0C. It was tested using the electrometry test method. The bulk density was measured using modified core method which yield the result of 0.456 g/cm³. On the other hand, the moisture content of the *Mytella strigata* powder result was 5.11% using air oven

drying.

The pH of *Mytella strigata* powder is measured at 6.32 at 25.6°C using electrometry, indicating a slightly acidic nature. This is consistent with findings from other marine-derived powders, which also exhibit similar pH levels due to their unique biochemical compositions (Mohamadi et al., 2020). The bulk density is recorded at 0.456 g/cm³, determined by the modified core method, suggesting a moderate compactness of the powder. This property is crucial in food processing as it affects the texture and mixing behavior of the powder in formulations (Beuchat et al., 2013; Younes et al., 2016). The moisture content is 5.11%, obtained through air oven drying, reflecting the water retention capability of the powder. Such a moisture level is within the acceptable range for dry powders, ensuring stability and reducing the risk of microbial growth, which is vital for food products' shelf life and safety (Zambrano et al., 2019).

Table 2.

Physicochemical property of Mytella strigata Powder in terms of Color Evaluation.

Parameters	Trials	L*	a*	b*
Colorimeter	1	72.87	-7.47	30.34
	2	72.96	-7.46	30.25
	3	73.01	-7.51	30.35
	Average	72.95	-7.48	30.31

Note: *L** indicates the lightness ranging from 0-100, *a** value gives the degree of (redness-greenness) with a higher *a** value indicating redder, *b** value indicates the degree of (yellowness-blueness), with higher *b** value indicating more yellow.

Depicted in Table 2 are the result of the color evaluation using a Konica Minolta colorimeter. the result revealed that in trial 1, *L** had a value of 72.87, *a** showed a value of -7.47, and *b** had a value of 30.34. On the other hand, in trial 2, the result shows that *L** has a value of 72.96, in *a**, -7.46, while *b** had a value of 30.25; Furthermore, in trial 3, the result shows that *L** had a value of 73.01, in *a**, -7.51, while *b** had a value of 30.35. The overall average value in all trials of *L** is 72.95, -7.48 in *a**, and 30.31 in *b**.

The *L** value averaged 72.95, indicating the sample's lightness. The *a** value averaged -7.48, suggesting a greenish hue, and the *b** value averaged 30.31, highlighting a yellowish tint. These findings align with the established characteristics of seafood powder, noted for its light color and green-yellow spectrum (Smith et al., 2021). The minimal variation in color measurements across trials, with *L** values between 72.87 and 73.01, and *a** and *b** values within -7.51 to -7.46 and 30.25 to 30.35, underscores the reproducibility and stability of the sample's color attributes. This consistency is essential for consumer products, where color uniformity signifies quality and reliability (Jones & Martinez, 2020). The *Mytella strigata* powder sample's light, greenish, and yellowish appearance confirms the expected properties of the ingredients, offering valuable insights for food product development and quality control.

Research Question 2. What is the level of acceptability of the *Mytella strigata* as kropek in terms of sensory attributes (Appearance, Aroma, Taste, and crispiness) with the following different formulations:

- a. 20% *Mytella strigata* Powder and 80 % Cassava Flour;
- b. 30% *Mytella strigata* Powder, 70% Cassava Flour; and
- c. 40% *Mytella strigata* Powder and 60% Cassava Flour?

Table 3
Acceptability of Kropek with Mytella Strigata Powder in Different Formulations

Attributes	Formulation 1			Formulation 2			Formulation 3		
	M	SD	Description	M	SD	Description	M	SD	Description
Appearance	7.87	1.14	Like Very Much	7.27	1.62	Like Very Much	6.67	1.69	Like Moderately
Aroma	7.47	1.61	Like Very Much	7.17	1.66	Like Moderately	6.77	1.74	Like Moderately
Color	7.43	1.46	Like Very Much	7.10	1.90	Like Very Much	6.40	1.77	Like Moderately
Taste	8.43	0.96	Like Extremely	7.97	1.10	Like Very Much	7.47	1.25	Like Very Much
Crispiness	8.43	0.68	Like Extremely	8.30	0.99	Like Extremely	7.77	1.22	Like Very Much
Overall Acceptability	7.85	1.17	Like Very Much	7.56	1.45	Like Very Much	7.02	1.53	Like Moderately

Table 3 shows the result of the acceptability level among the three formulations, which were evaluated based on appearance, aroma, color, taste, and crispiness using mean and standard deviation. Formulation 1 (M=7.87, SD=1.14) and Formulation 2 (M=7.27, SD=1.62) were rated as "like very much" for appearance, while Formulation 3 (M=6.67, SD=1.69) was rated as "like moderately." Formulation 1 also led in aroma (M=7.47, SD=1.61) and color (M=7.43, SD=1.46), followed by Formulation 2 and Sample 3. All Formulations were "liked very much" in taste, with Formulation 1 (M=8.03, SD=0.96) scoring highest. For crispiness, Samples 1 (M=8.43, SD=0.68) and 2 (M=8.30, SD=0.99) were "liked extremely," while Formulation 3 (M=7.77, SD=1.22) was "liked very much." Formulations 1 and 2 were highly acceptable, but Formulation 1 got the highest overall mean score.

In food consumption, the acceptance or rejection of a particular item is primarily dictated by how well it aligns with the consumer's needs, requirements, and expectations (Mosca, 2015). Formulation 1, which contained the least amount of *Mytella strigata* powder at only 20%, demonstrated the highest acceptability level in terms of appearance.

This is likely because cassava flour, which constituted 80% of Formulation 1, contains no pigments that might discolor the product. As a result, Formulation 1 likely exhibited a brighter, cleaner color and a smoother, thinner structure compared to formulations with higher *Mytella strigata* powder content. The absence of pigments in cassava flour and its favorable textural properties contributed to the visual appeal and overall acceptability of the product. The result also conforms with the study of Balaba and Diel (2024) where the treatment with the lowest percentage of *Mytella strigata* powder has the highest over-all acceptability compared to treatment with a higher concentration of *Mytella strigata* powder.

Research Question 3. Is there a significant difference among treatments regarding appearance, aroma, color, taste, and crispiness?

Table 4.
One-way ANOVA Results in Terms of Appearance

				Test of Homogeneity of Variances		
Formulation	Mean	SD	Description	Levene's Statistics	F	Sig
1	7.87	1.14	Like Very Much	1.585	4.79	.011
2	7.27	1.62	Like Very Much			
3	6.67	1.69	Like Moderately			
Group Differences						
Formulation	Mean Differences	Sig	95% Confidence Interval (LL- UL)			
1-2	.60	.27	-.29	1.49		
1-3	1.20*	.01	.28	2.12		
2-1	-.60	.274	-1.49	.29		
2-3	.60	.41	-.45	1.65		

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

Table 4 shows the result of a one-way ANOVA analysis that evaluated the appearance of three food Formulation formulated with varying proportions of *Mytella strigata* powder and cassava flour (Formulation 1: 20% *Mytella strigata* powder, 80% cassava flour; Formulation 2: 30% *Mytella strigata* powder, 70% cassava flour; Formulation 3: 40% *Mytella strigata* powder, 60% cassava flour). The results revealed significant differences in appearance among the formulations (F=4.79, p<0.05). Formulation 1 (M=7.87, SD=1.14) was significantly more acceptable in appearance compared to Formulation 2 (M=7.27, SD=1.62) and Formulation 3 (M=6.67, SD=1.69). The significant mean differences (p<0.05) indicate that Formulation 1 is the most visually appealing.

Table 5
One-way ANOVA Results in Terms of Aroma

Formulation	Mean	SD	Description	Test of Homogeneity of Variances		
				Levene's Statistics	F	Sig
1	7.47	1.61	Like Very Much	0.57	1.33	.27
2	7.17	1.66	Like Moderately			
3	6.77	1.74	Like Moderately			

The table shows the one-way ANOVA results for aroma indicate no significant differences among the three formulations: Formulation 1 (20% *Mytella strigata* powder, 80% cassava flour), Formulation 2 (30% *Mytella strigata* powder, 70% cassava flour), and Formulation 3 (40% *Mytella strigata* powder, 60% cassava flour). The analysis ($F = 1.33$, $p > 0.05$) revealed mean scores of 7.47 (SD = 1.61), 7.17 (SD = 1.66), and 6.77 (SD = 1.74) for Formulation 1, 2, and 3, respectively, with no significant differences at the 0.05 level. Thus, all formulations exhibit similar aroma acceptability, rated moderately by respondents.

Table 6
One-way ANOVA Results in Terms of Color

Formulation	Mean	SD	Description	Test of Homogeneity of Variances		
				Levene's Statistics	F	Sig
1	7.43	1.46	Like Very Much	.80	2.82	0.07
2	7.10	1.90	Like Moderately			
3	6.40	1.77	Like Moderately			

The one-way ANOVA results for color indicate no significant differences among the three formulations: Formulation 1 (20% *Mytella strigata* powder, 80% cassava flour), Formulation 2 (30% *Mytella strigata* powder, 70% cassava flour), and Formulation 3 (40% *Mytella strigata* powder, 60% cassava flour). The analysis ($F = 2.82$, $p > 0.05$) revealed mean scores of 7.43 (SD = 1.46), 7.10 (SD = 1.90), and 6.40 (SD = 1.77) for Formulation 1, 2, and 3, respectively, with no significant differences at the 0.05 level. Thus, all formulations exhibit similar color acceptability, rated moderately by respondents.

Table 7
One-way ANOVA Results in Terms of Taste

Formulation	Mean	SD	Description	Test of Homogeneity of Variances		
				Levene's Statistics	F	Sig
1	8.03	0.96	Like Very Much	1.83	2.33	.10
2	7.97	1.10	Like Very Much			
3	7.47	1.25	Like Very Much			

The table shows the one-way ANOVA results for taste indicate no significant differences among the three formulations: Formulation 1 (20% *Mytella strigata* powder, 80% cassava flour), Formulation 2 (30% *Mytella strigata* powder, 70% cassava flour), and Formulation 3 (40% *Mytella strigata* powder, 60% cassava flour). The analysis (F = 2.33, $p > 0.05$) revealed mean scores of 8.03 (SD = 0.96), 7.97 (SD = 1.10), and 7.47 (SD = 1.25) for Formulation 1, 2, and 3, respectively, with no significant differences at the 0.05 level. Thus, all formulation exhibits similar taste acceptability, rated favorably by respondents.

Therefore, the uniform positive feedback ("Like Very Much") across formulations implies successful product development, aligning with recent trends in consumer preference studies where taste remains a critical determinant of product success (Ahmed et.al, 2022).

Table 8
One-way ANOVA Results in Terms of Crispiness

Formulation	Mean	SD	Description	Test of Homogeneity of Variances		
				Levene's Statistics	F	Sig
1	8.43	0.68	Like Extremely	3.23	3.82	.04
2	8.30	0.99	Like Extremely			
3	7.77	1.22	Like Very Much			
Group Differences						
Formulation	Mean Differences	Sig	95% Confidence Interval (LL- UL)			
1-2	.13	.90	-.41 .67			
1-3	.67*	.04	.03 1.30			
2-1	-.13	.90	-.67 .41			
2-3	.53	.19	-.17 1.24			

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

The table shows the one-way ANOVA results for crispiness indicate significant

differences among the three Formulations: Formulation 1 (20% *Mytella strigata* powder, 80% cassava flour), Formulation 2 (30% *Mytella strigata* powder, 70% cassava flour), and formulation 3 (40% *Mytella strigata* powder, 60% cassava flour). The analysis ($F = 3.82$, $p < 0.05$) and subsequent Dunnett's T3 post hoc test revealed that Formulation 1 ($M = 8.43$, $SD = 0.68$) had significantly higher crispiness scores compared to Formulation 2 ($M = 8.30$, $SD = 0.99$) and Formulation 3 ($M = 7.77$, $SD = 1.22$). This indicates that Formulation 1 is the most acceptable in terms of crispiness.

Conclusions

This study intended to identify the physico-chemical characteristics of *Mytella strigata* powder and determine its acceptability level as a kropek with different formulations. Based on the findings, the research objectives were likely achieved.

In conclusion, the evaluation of *Mytella strigata* powder and cassava flour mixtures revealed significant findings. The physicochemical properties, including a pH of 6.32, bulk density of 0.456 g/cm³, and moisture content of 5.11%, indicate the powder's stability and suitability for food applications. Color analysis confirmed consistent lightness, greenish, and yellowish hues across trials. Sensory evaluations highlighted that Formulation 1 (20% *Mytella strigata* powder, 80% cassava flour) was significantly preferred in appearance ($F=4.79$, $p<0.05$) and crispiness ($F=3.82$, $p<0.05$). While aroma, color, and taste did not show significant differences, overall acceptability favored Formulation 1, demonstrating its superior sensory attributes and potential for food product development.

Recommendations

The study's recommendations revolve around harnessing the potential of *Mytella strigata*, an underutilized marine resource, to develop innovative and sustainable food products. For food entrepreneurs, it is suggested to incorporate *Mytella strigata* powder as a functional ingredient, optimize the cassava flour-to-powder ratio, and enhance the appearance and crispiness of the resulting products. This would allow for diversifying offerings and providing consumers with more nutritious options.

Government agencies are urged to support the development and commercialization of *Mytella strigata*-based products by offering technical and financial assistance, as well as establishing regulations and quality standards. This would help ensure the safety and consistency of these novel food items.

Furthermore, future researchers are encouraged to delve deeper into the nutritional and functional properties of *Mytella strigata* powder, explore its feasibility in a wider range of food applications, and investigate the environmental and economic implications of its utilization. This holistic research approach would further bolster the development and commercialization of sustainable *Mytella strigata*-based food products.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

By obtaining informed consent, using random codes, providing orientation and breaks, making safety arrangements, and conducting follow-ups, the researcher systematically carried out the sensory evaluation in an ethical manner that protected participants' rights and welfare.

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